

JOYFUL FOR YOU AND TENDER FOR US: THE INFLUENCE OF INDIVIDUAL CHARACTERISTICS AND LANGUAGE ON EMOTION LABELING AND CLASSIFICATION

Juan Sebastián Gómez-Cañón¹ Estefanía Cano²
 Perfecto Herrera¹ Emilia Gómez^{3,1}

¹ Music Technology Group, Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Spain

² Songquito UG, Erlangen, Germany

³ European Commission, Joint Research Centre, Seville, Spain

juansebastian.gomez@upf.edu

Quadrant*	Emotion	Query Synonym	Lang.	Artist – Song	BPM**	A [-1, 1]**	V [-1, 1]**
Q1 (A+V+)	Joyful activation	joy	Eng.	Taio Cruz - Dynamite	119.98	0.57	0.63
			Eng.	Miami Sound Machine - Conga	122.24	0.31	0.73
	Power	-	Eng.	Ultra Montanes - Anyway	-	-	-
			Eng.	Rose Tattoo - Rock n Roll Outlaw	93.06	0.54	0.23
			Eng.	The Jordanares - Hound Dog	180.67	0.33	0.04
Surprise	-	Eng.	Shakira - Animal City	140.03	0.65	0.78	
		Eng.	Disincarnate - In Sufferance	86.79	0.90	-0.74	
Q2 (A+V-)	Anger	angry	Inst.	Obituary - Redneck Stomp	91.06	0.72	-0.03
			Inst.	Joe Henry - Nico Lost One Small Buddha	98.72	0.33	0.26
	Fear	anguished	Eng.	Silverstein - Worlds Apart	129.91	0.46	-0.06
			Eng.	Pennywise - Pennywise	94.28	0.97	0.31
			Eng.	Squeeze - Here Comes That Feeling	134.03	0.46	-0.42
Tension	tense	Eng.	Liz Phair - Divorce Song	120.37	0.69	0.42	
		Eng.	Lou Reed - Heroine	76.56	-0.53	-0.65	
Q3 (A-V-)	Bitterness	bitter	Eng.	Motorhead - Dead and Gone	102.64	0.43	0.22
			Spa.	Juan Luis Guerra - Sobremesa	82.36	-0.46	-0.70
	Sadness	sad	Eng.	Jim Brickman - Simple Things	91.99	0.26	0.29
Spa.			Gloria Estefan - Mi Buen Amor	119.94	-0.22	0.19	
Q4 (A-V+)	Peace	-	Eng.	Celine Dion - Beautiful Boy	111.05	-0.10	0.21
			Spa.	Beyonce - Amor Gitano	167.88	0.49	0.19
	Tenderness	gentle	Eng.	Steven Chapman - Made for Worshipping	102.89	0.55	-0.56
			Eng.	Matisyahu - On Nature	97.01	0.64	0.30
			Eng.	Transcendence	spiritual		

Table 1. Song selection with emotion and quadrant information for annotation analysis, including synonyms for query and lyrics language. * refers to the annotation in the 4Q emotion data set. ** refers to audio features retrieved from the Spotify API: beats per minute (BPM), energy (A), and valence (V). Values in *italics* show disagreement between the original annotations and Spotify audio features. We normalized the range for energy and valence to [-1,1] for comparison purposes.

Factors	Eng. (26)	Spa. (56)	Man. (27)	Ger. (17)	All (126)
F1 - Active Engagement (range: [9, 63], $\mu = 41.52$)	39.85 ($\sigma = 12.72$)	40.14 ($\sigma = 10.45$)	40.78 ($\sigma = 9.27$)	40.18 ($\sigma = 12.70$)	40.22 ($\sigma = 11.06$)
F2 - Perceptual Abilities (range: [9, 63], $\mu = 50.20$)	52.00 ($\sigma = 8.62$)	49.64 ($\sigma = 8.40$)	49.30 ($\sigma = 8.46$)	53.29 ($\sigma = 8.14$)	50.55 ($\sigma = 8.55$)
F3 - Musical Training (range: [7, 49], $\mu = 26.52$)	29.23 ($\sigma = 12.54$)	24.55 ($\sigma = 11.68$)	23.56 ($\sigma = 9.23$)	30.65 ($\sigma = 10.56$)	26.13 ($\sigma = 11.56$)
F4 - Emotions (range: [6, 42], $\mu = 34.66$)	34.00 ($\sigma = 7.45$)	34.98 ($\sigma = 4.45$)	33.67 ($\sigma = 5.50$)	34.06 ($\sigma = 4.67$)	34.37 ($\sigma = 5.48$)
F5 - Singing Abilities (range: [7, 49], $\mu = 31.67$)	33.08 ($\sigma = 10.83$)	30.54 ($\sigma = 8.87$)	33.19 ($\sigma = 7.51$)	32.12 ($\sigma = 10.12$)	31.84 ($\sigma = 9.30$)
F6 - General sophistication (range: [18, 126], $\mu = 81.58$)	84.58 ($\sigma = 23.39$)	77.88 ($\sigma = 20.01$)	82.78 ($\sigma = 17.49$)	85.94 ($\sigma = 23.89$)	81.40 ($\sigma = 21.08$)

Table 2. Music Sophistication Index results for participants in each language. We report mean and standard deviation for each factor. First column reports the possible ranges of each score and population means from the original study.

		anger	bitter	fear	joy	peace	power	sad	surprise	tender	tension	transc.
Median Test	N	2772	2772	2772	2772	2772	2772	2772	2772	2772	2772	2772
	df	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
	Median	2.00	2.00	1.50	3.00	2.00	3.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
	Chi-Square	63.000	20.789	12.636	5.358	4.010	100.654	13.474	13.302	16.071	45.725	11.531
	Asymp. Sig.	0.0005**	0.0005**	0.005**	0.147	0.260	0.0005**	0.004**	0.004**	0.001**	0.0005**	0.009**
Kruskal-Wallis Test	Chi-Square	46.139	13.107	12.396	6.063	7.084	152.318	12.193	10.414	21.627	31.703	20.922
	Asymp. Sig.	0.0005**	0.004**	0.006**	0.109	0.069	0.0005**	0.007**	0.015**	0.0005**	0.0005**	0.0005**
M-W (Eng.-Ger.)	Z	-0.267	-1.185	-0.044	-2.186	-2.243	-8.521	-0.725	-2.960	0.000	-1.696	-0.281
	Asymp. Sig.	0.790	0.236	0.965	0.029	0.025	0.0005***	0.468	0.003***	1.000	0.090	0.779
M-W (Eng.-Man.)	Z	-2.221	-1.653	-0.430	-0.090	-2.241	-4.199	-1.812	-1.875	-0.305	-1.080	-1.471
	Asymp. Sig.	0.026	0.098	0.667	0.928	0.025	0.0005***	0.070	0.061	0.761	0.280	0.141
M-W (Eng.-Spa.)	Z	-4.048	-1.413	-2.534	-0.749	-1.969	-3.297	-2.528	-0.684	-3.700	-3.689	-3.765
	Asymp. Sig.	0.0005***	0.158	0.011	0.454	0.049	0.001***	0.011	0.494	0.0005***	0.0005***	0.0005***
M-W (Ger.-Man.)	Z	-1.516	-0.219	-0.383	-2.243	-0.316	-11.583	-2.226	-1.190	-0.256	-2.645	-1.563
	Asymp. Sig.	0.130	0.826	0.701	0.025	0.752	0.0005***	0.026	0.234	0.798	0.008***	0.118
M-W (Spa.-Man.)	Z	-3.471	-2.409	-2.131	-1.772	-0.883	-6.609	-2.801	-2.589	-2.982	-5.065	-3.513
	Asymp. Sig.	0.001***	0.016	0.033	0.076	0.377	0.0005***	0.005***	0.010	0.003	0.0005***	0.0005***
M-W (Spa.-Man.)	Z	-6.324	-3.224	-2.925	-0.855	-0.626	-7.885	-0.576	-1.386	-3.360	-2.517	-1.996
	Asymp. Sig.	0.0005***	0.001***	0.003***	0.393	0.531	0.0005***	0.564	0.166	0.001***	0.012	0.046

Table 3. Results from Median Test and Kruskal-Wallis H Test: German ($N = 374$), English ($N = 572$), Mandarin ($N = 594$), Spanish ($N = 1232$). Significance at $p < 0.01$ is depicted with **. Consecutive pairwise Mann-Whitney U Tests (M-W) were performed with Bonferroni correction $\alpha = 0.05/6$ yielding significance at $p \leq 0.00833$ and depicted with ***.

		anger	bitter	fear	joy	peace	power	sad	surprise	tender	tension	transc.	
Pearson Correlation	anger	1	.550**	.531**	-.301**	-.418**	.277**	.085**	.130**	-.344**	.553**	-.065**	
	bitter		1	.572**	-.449**	-.189**	-0.019	.482**	0.018	-.074**	.348**	0.032	
	fear			1	-.349**	-.181**	.070**	.336**	.143**	-.097**	.433**	.080**	
	joy				1	.214**	.303**	-.420**	.225**	.113**	-.206**	.114**	
	peace					1	-.182**	.148**	-0.010	.645**	-.383**	.356**	
	power						1	-.260**	.313**	-.183**	.241**	.143**	
	sad							1	-.043*	.292**	.059**	.177**	
	surprise								1	-0.009	.289**	.228**	
	tender									1	-.322**	.424**	
	tension										1	0.025	
	transc.											1	
	Spearman's rho	anger	1	.580**	.577**	-.281**	-.384**	.269**	.133**	.159**	-.313**	.546**	-0.029
		bitter		1	.605**	-.441**	-.174**	-0.012	.492**	.045*	-.065**	.363**	.055**
fear				1	-.328**	-.146**	.077**	.368**	.180**	-.068**	.445**	.115**	
joy					1	.225**	.298**	-.408**	.226**	.121**	-.196**	.118**	
peace						1	-.185**	.166**	0.023	.651**	-.363**	.373**	
power							1	-.253**	.303**	-.187**	.239**	.134**	
sad								1	0.001	.300**	.089**	.202**	
surprise									1	0.021	.303**	.258**	
tender										1	-.303**	.432**	
tension											1	.050**	
transc.												1	

Table 4. Cross-correlations between ratings of emotion for music with lyrics in English. Significance at $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$ are depicted with * and **, respectively.

Pop/Rock Emotion Perception | 8% of items completed

▶ 0:00 / 0:30

Please play the audio excerpt. Rate the emotions that you **perceive**:

Explanation of emotions:

Anger: I perceive the music as angry, annoying, frustrating.

Bitterness: I perceive the music as hostile, distressing, painful.

Fear: I perceive the music as alarming, anxious, afraid.

Joyful activation: I perceive the music as animating, bouncy, dancing, amusing, stimulating.

Peacefulness: I perceive the music as serene, calm, relaxed.

Power: I perceive the music as energetic, fiery, heroic.

Sadness: I perceive the music as sad, tearful, sorrowful.

Surprise: I perceive the music as astonishing, exciting, surprising.

Tenderness: I perceive the music as tender, serene, sympathetic.

Tension: I perceive the music as tense, agitating, irritating.

Transcendence: I perceive the music as overwhelming, inspiring, spiritual.

	Completely disagree	Disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Agree	Completely agree
Anger	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Bitterness	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Fear	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Joyful activation	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Peacefulness	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Power	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Sadness	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Surprise	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Tenderness	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Tension	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Transcendence	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I like this excerpt.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I know this excerpt.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I understood the lyrics of this excerpt the first time I heard it.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

Figure 1. Example of web survey in English.

Figure 2. Resulting distribution of centroids after factor analysis. Emotions belonging to quadrants result with closer centroids: Q1 (joy, surprise, power), Q2 (anger, fear, tension), Q3 (sadness, bitterness), and Q4 (peace, tenderness, transcendence).

Figure 3. Example of clustering in 3D with MDS with positive emotion perception score. Top left: resulting embeddings from manifold learning, top right: kept embeddings in color and removed in grey, bottom left: remaining embeddings, bottom right: resulting clusters using K-Means.

Figure 4. Example of clustering in 2D with MDS with positive familiarity. Top left: resulting embeddings from manifold learning, top right: kept embeddings in color and removed in grey, bottom left: remaining embeddings, bottom right: resulting clusters using K-Means.

Figure 5. Example of clustering in 2D with UMAP with positive lyrics comprehension. Top left: resulting embeddings from manifold learning, top right: kept embeddings in color and removed in grey, bottom left: remaining embeddings, bottom right: resulting clusters using K-Means.